

Deliverable 4.1.1.1

OVERVIEW OF METADATA & ONTOLOGY INTERACTION WITH
NFDI4ENERGY SERVICES

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General Information

Summary

Within the NFDI4Energy consortium, Task Area 4 focuses on the development of ontologies and metadata schemas for energy system research. These resources assist in cataloging research artifacts such as datasets and papers, making scientific works easier to find and share.

To better understand the requirements for the ontologies and schemas, TA4 reviewed the planned collection of NFDI4Energy services and evaluated which of the services might benefit from the integration of an ontology or a metadata schema and which already have integrated such resources. The results of this evaluation are documented here.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

This deliverable assists with the requirements documentation for TA4's planned semantic artifacts (Measures 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.5), as well as the simulation software ontology of TA5 (Measure 5.2). It also serves as reference material for the service development teams in TA8, tracking which services may require coordination with TA4 and TA5 for ontology/metadata support during implementation.

Deliverable

TA4 approached the task of creating this overview by first collecting a list of NFDI4Energy services from the consortium's service portfolio website (<https://nfdi4energy.uol.de/services-and-resources/>). In the June 2025 TA4 quarterly meeting, members of TA4 went through the list one service at a time and discussed whether or not each service would benefit from the integration of a metadata schema and/or ontologies (either a domain ontology, or a more subject-specific ontology). The results of this discussion are documented in the table presented here.

	NFDI4Energy Service	Metadata Schema Needed?	Ontology Needed?	Comments
Existing Services	Open Research Knowledge Graph	Yes – for datasets	Yes	
	Leibniz Data Manager	Yes – for datasets	Optional	The metadata schema is needed for registering data sets. Some ontology annotations at the data set level may be possible to implement, if desired.
	Open Energy Database	Yes – for datasets	Yes	The metadata schema is needed for registering data sets. Ontology annotation capabilities are already implemented.
	Open Energy Databus	Yes – for datasets	Yes	
	RDMO4Energy	Yes – for datasets and for software	No	
	Open Energy Scenario Bundles	Yes – for datasets	Yes	
	Terminology Service (TS)	No	Yes	This service is the primary registry for the ontologies used by the other services for annotations.
Future Services	Anonymization Service	Yes – for datasets	No	
	Competence4Energy	No	No	
	Simulation-as-a-Service Hub	Yes – for software	Yes	
	Software Metadata Extraction and Curation Software (SMECS)	Yes – for software	Yes	

References

Nieße, A., Ferenz, S., Auer, S., Dähling, S., Decker, S., Dorfner, J., German, R., Gütlein, M., Hagenmeyer, V., Henni, S., Lehnhoff, S., Lilliestam, J., Lu, L., Mey, F., Monti, A., Muschner, C., Reinkensmeier, J., Richter, M., Schäfer, M., ... Zilles, J. (2022). nfdi4energy – National Research Data Infrastructure for the Interdisciplinary Energy System Research (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772013>